

Effect of Climate Change on Potential Distribution of *Cedrus libani* A. Rich in the 21st century: an Ecological Niche Modeling assessment

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Abstract: The present study is focused on the potential distribution of the Lebanese cedar (*Cedrus libani*) in the present and in the future throughout the 21st century. The location of this work encompasses Lebanon, Syria and Turkey. Twenty-four environmental variables are used and two Representative Concentration Pathways (RCP) scenarios for two different time periods are studied: RCP 4.5 2050, RCP 4.5 2070, RCP 8.5 2050 and RCP 8.5 2070. The most interesting novelty is the use of 13 General Circulation Models (GCMs) and 6 algorithms (Climate Space Model [CSM], Envelope Score [EnvScore], Environmental Distance [EnvDist], Genetic Algorithm for Rule-set Production [GARP], Maximum Entropy [MaxEnt] and Support Vector Machines [SVM]) considered for modelling. Area Under the Curve (AUC) is as goodness of fit and building the final consensus map. The global habitat suitability area would enlarge in the forecasted scenarios with respect to the present, although it would be more restricted in 2070 due to the altitudinal shift. This study also suggests an interesting approach to manage *C. libani* stands by means of afforestation programs aiming to face global warming in the late 21st century.

Keywords: Ecological Niche Modeling; potential distribution; forecasting; climate change; Near East; *Cedrus libani*

39 **1. Introduction**

40 The *Cedrus* genus comprises four species with a disjunct distribution in several areas of the
41 Northern Hemisphere. A combination of southerly migrated populations from the high latitude area
42 of Eurasia during climatic oscillations in the Tertiary and further fragmentation and dispersal of
43 these populations (Qiao et al. 2007) has resulted in the present distribution of these species: *Cedrus*
44 *atlantica* (Endl.) Manetti ex Carrie' re in southern Mediterranean (Algeria and Morocco), *Cedrus*
45 *brevifolia* (Hook. f.) Henry in Cyprus, *Cedrus libani* A. Rich. in Turkey, Lebanon and Syria and *Cedrus*
46 *deodara* (Roxb.) G. Don in Himalaya.

47 *Cedrus libani* is a prominent tree species native to the Eastern Mediterranean Basin that covers
48 large areas of Southern Turkey, Western Syria and Lebanon and has been subject to persistent
49 decimation of its forests for wood exploitation since antiquity (Giordano 1956; Chaney and Basbous
50 1978; Senitza 1989; Talhouk et al. 2001; Boydak 2003; Fady et al. 2008). Its relevance as a keystone
51 species in the mountain chains of the Near East, and its historical connection with civilizations living
52 and exploiting that region since the Egyptians and Phoenicians, made the cedar a symbol of
53 longevity, holiness and peace. Unfortunately the species is assessed as vulnerable under the IUCN
54 red listing due to its limited area of occupancy, a decline in its habitat quality and the loss of mature
55 individuals due to grazing by goats, urbanization, selective cutting, pest outbreaks and damages
56 caused by winter sports (Gardner 2016). In Lebanon (around 1,000,000 ha), the current fragmented
57 cedar groves are 5% of the original distribution range (Khuri et al. 2000) and the remnants of more
58 than 500,000 ha of post-glacial forest (Alptekin et al. 1997; Fady et al. 2008); Lebanese cedar
59 populations are located mostly on the western slopes of Mount Lebanon, at elevations between 1100
60 and 1950 m, covering barely 2,200 ha and constituting the southern limit of its area of distribution
61 (Talhouk et al. 2001). Most of the cedar forests are in Turkey, which cover large areas of the Taurus
62 Mountains, between 460 and 2400 m, in addition to 2 remnant populations in the Black Sea region at
63 elevations between 700 and 1400m that are considered the northern limits of the cedar's natural area
64 of extent. Apart from this natural distribution area, there are some isolated planted cedar stands in
65 Inner Anatolia. In total, the Turkish cedar forests cover 463,521 ha and constitute 90% of the area of
66 occupancy of the species (Boydak 2003; Hajar et al. 2010; Ayan et al. 2016; Ayan et al. 2017; Ekici et al.
67 2017). In Syria, cedar stands are rare, only covering 150 ha, located on the eastern slopes of the
68 Aleouite Mountains, between 1300 and 1550 m (Khouzami et al. 1994). The optimal altitudinal zone
69 for *C. libani* is situated between 800 and 2100 m, with fewer stands below or above those limits, and
70 therefore located between the supra Mediterranean and Mediterranean montane vegetation levels
71 while stands at higher elevations are situated in the oro Mediterranean where per humid, humid,
72 sub-humid and semiarid bioclimatic conditions prevail (Senitza 1989; Quézel and Médail 2003;
73 Blondel et al. 2010).

74 Cedar thrives in pure stands, or mixed with other conifers such as *Abies cilicica* (Antoine &
75 Kotschy) Carrière, *Juniperus excelsa* M. Bieb. and *J. foetidissima* Willd. or broad-leaved oak species like
76 *Quercus cerris* L. and *Q. petraea* subsp. *pinnatifida* (K.Koch) Menitsky (known also as *Q. cedrorum*). On
77 lower altitudes it is mixed with *Pinus nigra* subsp. *pallasiana* (Lamb.) Holmboe, and *P. brutia* Ten.; on
78 lower latitudes towards its southern limits in Lebanon it is also mixed with *Q. look* Kotschy and *Q.*
79 *kotschyana* O. Schwarz (Khouzami 1994; Blondel et al. 2010; Abi Saleh et al. 1996; Oner and Uysal
80 2009; Farjon 2010).

81 The cedar of Lebanon grows well under a Mediterranean climate in areas with winter rain and
82 snow, with peak monthly precipitations between November and February and a dry period in
83 summer (Senitza 1989; Atalay 2002). Although average annual rainfall in the different cedar stands
84 vary from 540 mm up to 1500 mm, the growth is highly affected by spring precipitation patterns and
85 snowmelt (Hajar et al. 2010; Ducrey et al. 2008; Touchan et al. 2005). Cedar tolerates a wide range of
86 temperatures, ranging from -15 to 7.5 °C with extremes of -35 °C in winter, and 40 °C in summer
87 (Ducrey et al. 2008).

88 In Lebanon, the cedar can thrive on alkaline and acidic soils, with no striking difference. It may
89 also be found in karstic-dolomitic rock formations (Abi Saleh et al. 1996). Mainly, *C. libani* prefers
90 carbonate soils with pH between 6.6 and 8.2 (Ayasligil 1997) but also grows on soils with parent

91 materials consisting of sandstones, mica schist, serpentine and olivine basalt (Sevim 1955). Due to its
92 relative wide range of distribution and its relative plasticity towards climate extremes, coupled with
93 its importance as a major species for timber production, Messinger et al. (2015) investigated its
94 introduction into Central Europe as a promising species for timber production and for ecosystem
95 services, under a changing climate.

96 Cedar has been widely used in reforestation activities in Turkey and Lebanon, as a major
97 species for ecosystem restoration and for the increase of forest cover (Khuri et al. 2000; Boydak 2003;
98 Ayan et al. 2017). Many programs were devoted to extend the occupancy area of cedar outside its
99 natural range, especially in Central Anatolia (Oner and Uysal 2009). Those actions, which required
100 investments in reforestation by planting and sowing with carpels, doubled the cedar surface in
101 Turkey. In Lebanon, the national master plan for land use has foreseen a “cedar and fruit trees
102 corridor” on the western slopes of Mount Lebanon, between 1400 and 1900 m.

103 In order to optimize these initiatives, it is important to understand the bioclimatic niche and
104 distribution of *C. libani* at present and under future climate. Such projections might be achieved after
105 a full data collection of present species distribution, which is of paramount importance to clarify the
106 conservation status and the degree of threat the species is facing. Applying ENM (Ecological Niche
107 Modeling) can provide further insights into species’ potential distribution and offer the possibility
108 for foresters to plan forthcoming projects devoted to extend the actual distribution, identify new
109 areas where cedar would be able to grow and identify current areas where the species might suffer
110 from changes in climate conditions (Guisan and Zimmermann 2000; Hernández et al. 2006; Pearson
111 et al. 2007). Correlative approaches are the base for developing ENM, where field observations and
112 environmental variables are used to produce statistically-derived response surfaces. Outputs
113 represent a model that approximates the species’ distribution, and/or its ecological niche sensu
114 Hutchinson (Hutchinson 1957) in case of a forecasting approximation (Soberón 2010; Sillero 2011).
115 This work has been carried out considering 13 GCMs and 6 algorithms conferring robustness.

116 In view of this, this paper aims to: (i) provide an approximate but reliable distribution of actual
117 cedar stands in the Near East considering political instability, (ii) project and map its future habitat
118 suitability using ENM based on environmental variables, and (iii) evaluate the spatial distribution of
119 reputed best areas to increase cedar’s distribution by new plantations. It must be emphasized that
120 this work is addressing the potential distribution of *C. libani*. Therefore, habitat suitability according
121 to the explanatory variables is detected; no biotic interactions are considered because they cannot be
122 explicitly incorporated into ENMs.

123 2. Materials and Methods

124 2.1. Study area

125 The study area is located in the Near East including Lebanon, Syria and Turkey (Figure 1a). All
126 the existing populations are within the study area, mainly on the coastal ranges of Lebanon and
127 Syria, between 1,300 and 1,950 m. Most of the populations are on the western slopes, facing the sea,
128 with few on the leeward established direction. Apart from this natural distribution area, there are
129 many artificial cedar stands establishing mainly through planting in Aegean, Marmara, Black Sea
130 and Inner and Eastern Anatolian regions of Turkey. They were included in this study because they
131 thrive and show good health. Orography is rough within the area of distribution of the cedar. Mount
132 Taurus range culminates at 3,916 m a.s.l. in Erciyes peak, Mount Lebanon reaches 3,088 m a.s.l.,
133 while Nusayriyah mountain in Syria barely summits at 1,575 m a.s.l.

135 **FIGURE 1**

137 2.2. Input data

138 Twenty-four environmental variables were considered for *C. libani* occurrence (Table 1). Among
139 them, 3 explanatory variables were topographic (elevation, aspect and slope). A Digital Elevation
140 Model (DEM) at 70 m resolution, from ASTER (Advanced Spaceborne Thermal Emission and
141 Reflection Radiometer) GDEM available at <https://asterweb.jpl.nasa.gov/gdem.asp>, was used to

142 compute both aspect and slope by the *3D Analyst* function implemented in ArcMap 9.3.1. We used
143 WGS84_UTM_Zone 34N projected coordinate system. The remaining 21 variables were: (i) 19
144 climatic factors downloaded from WorldClim 1.4 project (Hijmans et al. 2005) plus (ii) 2 indexes
145 (Emberger and Continentality) which were used in the modeling process because estimators of
146 additional climatic parameters were not included in the WorldClim's dataset. They were calculated
147 from the relative formulas as follows:

148
149
$$Q \text{ (Emberger index)} = \frac{2000 \times P}{M^2 - m^2},$$

150
151
152 where P is the annual rainfall, M^2 is the mean of the maximum temperatures of the warmest month,
153 and m^2 is the mean of the minimum temperatures of the coldest month (López-Tirado et al. 2018).

154
155 Conrad Index of Continentality (C_i) was retrieved from the difference between the mean
156 temperatures of warmest (M) and coldest months (m), divided by the sine of the latitude (φ) of the
157 centre of each cell forming the study area (Conrad 1946). The formula is:

158
159
$$C_i = \frac{[1.7 (M - m)]}{\sin (\varphi + 10^\circ)} - 14.$$

160
161 Raw data in TIFF (Tagged Image File Format) was converted into ASCII (American Standard
162 Code for Information Interchange) format to be used in the modeling software *openModeller Desktop*
163 *v1.5.0*.

164
165 **TABLE 1**

166
167 Occurrence data of *C. libani* in the Near East were assembled from different databases, personal
168 observations and interpretation of aerial photography. Specifically, populations in Lebanon were
169 retrieved from the forest map (MOA 2005), checked and updated by field trips and
170 photo-interpretation. Additional information, such as centroids' coordinates, polygon surface in
171 hectares and site toponyms, was available in the database. Turkish distribution of cedar was also
172 collected from (OGM 2015) as polygons with metadata about surfaces, coordinates and toponyms.
173 Cedar forests in Syria were the hardest to collect and verify, due to known recent political turmoil in
174 that area. Previous investigations made the starting point of an accurate aerial photo-interpretation
175 by satellite images. Given the impossibility to verify the real extent of each cedar forest in Syria, such
176 an a priori reconstruction might be considered imperfect, thus over or underestimating the true
177 species occurrence in that country. However, we believe the number of polygons collected in this
178 investigation significantly approximates the distribution in Syria. We did our best to approach the
179 distribution of *C. libani* in the study area.

180 Polygons were gathered and stored into a geodatabase to work with ArcMap 9.3.1. On the other
181 hand, a shapefile of polygons was created from a random explanatory variable raster at 30
182 arc-seconds resolution. Then *C. libani* polygons were intersected with the vector grid by means of
183 *select by location* tool of this software. The selected grids were saved as a new polygon Shapefile,
184 which was the base to build a point (centroid) Shapefile using *shapes to centroids* from *XTool Pro*
185 extension. A total of 16,363 equidistant points were retrieved as the current distribution of *C. libani*
186 in the study area. Finally, coordinates associated to each point were then saved in a CSV
187 (Comma-Separated Values) file to be submitted to the modeling software.

188
189 *2.3. Ecological Niche Modeling and goodness of fit*

190
191 The software *openModeller Desktop v1.1.0* was used in a first step to model *C. libani* for the
192 present period. This software encompasses several algorithms from which 6 were run: Climate

193 Space Model (CSM), Envelope Score (EnvScore), Environmental Distance (EnvDist), Genetic
194 Algorithm for Rule-set Production (GARP), Maximum Entropy (MaxEnt) and Support Vector
195 Machines (SVM). Other algorithms were approached at the beginning such as Niche Mosaic, Bioclim
196 and Environmental Niche Factor Analysis (ENFA), although then dismissed because of non-reliable
197 results. A consensus map across the six algorithms was built following the equation (Vessella et al.
198 2015; Vessella et al. 2017; López-Tirado et al. 2018):
199

$$200 \quad X_{pond} = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n z_i AUC_i}{\sum_{i=1}^n AUC_i},$$

201
202 where X_{pond} is the weighted probability of habitat suitability, z_i is the probability of the potential
203 occurrence of the cell of the i -model and AUC_i is the Area Under the Curve.

204 AUC values were also used to validate the models according to Swets (1988) who established
205 the following intervals: 0.5–0.7 as low accuracy; 0.7–0.9 as potentially useful; and >0.9 as high
206 accuracy.

207 The final consensus map for the present plus the expected future explanatory variables
208 downloaded from WorldClim 1.4 project (Hijmans et al. 2005) were the base for building the
209 scenario maps along the 21st century –reclassified in ten intervals by means of ArcMap 9.3.1. The
210 latter were performed in two RCPs (Representative Concentration Pathways), each one in two time
211 slices. These scenarios represent the concentration of greenhouse gases and pollutants resulting from
212 human activity, adopted by the Fifth Assessment Report (IPCC 2014). The most extreme and an
213 intermediate scenario were selected: the former achieving 8.5 W/m² by 2100 (RCP 8.5), while the
214 latter an increase of 4.5 W/m² (RCP 4.5), also in the same deadline. Two time slices were studied for
215 each RCP: 2050 (average for 2041–2060) and 2070 (average for 2061–2080). In total, two scenarios
216 were forecasted for two different periods (RCP 4.5 2050, RCP 4.5 2070, RCP 8.5 2050 and RCP 8.5
217 2070). On the other hand, the climatic explanatory variables used resulted from merging 13 Global
218 Circulation Models (GCMs) calibrated for the Northern Hemisphere: ACCESS1-0, BCC-CSM1-1,
219 CCSM4, CNRM-CM5, GFDL-CM3, GISS-E2-R, HadGEM2-ES, INMCM4, IPSL-CM5A-LR, MIROC5,
220 MPI-ESM-LR, MRI-CGCM3 and NorESM1-M.

221 3. Results

222 The total study area spans ca. 978,202 km² within which the observed occurrence of *C. libani*
223 only reaches 0.39%. Our results state a greater potential distribution of this species in the present
224 reaching the 9.46% of the whole territory in the consensus map for those cells above 50% of
225 suitability. The habitat suitability area for the future scenarios is increased as well ranging from
226 21.04% to 41.66% (see Table 2 for the results in km²). The potentially suitable habitat of *C. libani* in the
227 present occurs along Southern Turkey, where most of the stands are found today, and not reaching
228 the top of the mountains (Figure 1b).
229

230 TABLE 2

231
232 Figure 2 shows the output maps for the RCPs scenarios. All the scenarios follow similar trends
233 with respect to Figure 1b: (i) a greater habitat suitability area, and (ii) a higher elevation and latitude
234 (cf. Table 2). As can be noted in Figure 1b the maximum value reached was 80%. In other words, no
235 cells with 100% for each algorithm were found.

236 According to our results, Central-Northern Turkish ranges become more suitable for the
237 growth of *C. libani* in the forecasted scenarios. On the other hand, Southern Turkish ranges loose
238 potential distribution at lower elevations whilst summits are reached by this conifer. The total
239 habitat suitability area is decreased gradually from the intermediate emission scenario (RCP 4.5) in
240 2050 to the hard emission scenario (RCP 8.5) in 2070 (Table 2). Regarding Syria and Lebanon, the
241 main potential stands of *C. libani* are found in coastal ranges that are influenced by the

242 Mediterranean climate. Inner areas of Syria do not exhibit any potentiality due to the arid conditions
243 –poor occurrence data must be taken into account in this country.

244 245 **FIGURE 2**

246
247 The suitability variation map among the 6 algorithms used to build the consensus map for the
248 current time period is shown as supplementary material (Figure S1). Standard Deviation (S.D.) has
249 been used scoring maximum values between 0.41 and 0.44% in some coastal areas of the whole
250 territory and inner areas of Turkey. Goodness of fit of the 6 algorithms was assessed by means of the
251 AUC scores. EnvDis and SVM were the most accurate algorithms whereas EnvScore and MaxEnt
252 showed lower values (Table 3).

253 254 **TABLE 3**

255
256 Figure 3 shows the surface occupancy in the present and both emission scenarios and periods
257 respectively. The four studied scenarios follow a similar tendency where peaks (ca. 20-27% of
258 surface occupancy) are reached at 40-50% of suitability. Between RCP 4.5 and RCP 8.5, only the latter
259 exceeds the 25% of surface occupancy in cells of ca. 40% of suitability. Present period differs from the
260 future scenarios showing lower surface occupancy at this point of suitability. The highest values are
261 found around 32% of suitability. Finally, the highest suitability (over 60%) presents lower surface
262 occupancy (around 0-10%) for the five models.

263

264 **4. Discussion**

265 Ecological Niche Modeling has been widely used in the last decades to understand spatial and
266 temporal potential distribution of the species. Most of these theoretical approaches focus on
267 forecasting due to the expected global climate change along the twenty-first century. The
268 Mediterranean Basin would suffer a generalized rising of the mean temperatures whereas rainfall
269 would undergo irregular patterns (IPCC 2014). In addition, Regato and Salman (2008) state that
270 Mediterranean mountainous areas are at the forefront of global climate change (increasing drought
271 effect, rising and fluctuating temperatures, irregular and heavy precipitation, etc.) in the world.
272 Recent studies have demonstrated that mountain species such as *Cedrus atlantica* are persisting in
273 restricted and isolated areas considered as microrefugia (Cheddadi et al. 2017). Increasing drought
274 effects are harmful to sensitive species like mountain conifers and *Cedrus* in particular (Linares et al.
275 2013). Ulbrich et al. (2006) examines various scenarios; in the Mediterranean Basin, towards the end
276 of the century, the net water shortage may increase by 1.3-1.4%, while the annual rainfall may
277 decrease by 10-30%. At this point, we have centered on an emblematic cedar (*C. libani*) from the Near
278 East which could be affected by the changing conditions in the next decades.

279 The use of planted stands was justified because they grow and thrive, therefore they fit habitat
280 as the natural stands do. Thirteen GCMs calibrated for the Northern Hemisphere and 6 different
281 algorithms confer robustness to this work. This methodology has already been proven and achieved
282 previously (López-Tirado et al. 2018). Goodness of fit of the models was executed by the AUC
283 showing disparate scores and only two algorithms displayed a value under 0.7 (Table 3), i.e.
284 indicating low accuracy according to Swets (1988). Nonetheless, they were considered in the
285 consensus map because: (i) their value was close to the threshold (0.68 and 0.64 for EnvScore and
286 MaxEnt respectively) and (ii) their weight in the final consensus map was lower according to the
287 equation showed in *Materials and Methods* section.

288 Surface occupancy follows similar trends by period (2050 and 2070) in the two emission
289 scenarios. It can be noted from figure 3 how present shows the highest surface occupancy at lower
290 suitability class with respect to both future periods. According to these results, *C. libani* could find
291 wider suitable areas than in the current period. The increase in the area covered by middle
292 suitability (40%) when compared to the present situation could be related to the shifting in latitude

293 in the area of extent of *C. libani*. The cedar would reach larger areas in the northern part of Turkey
294 under Euxinian climate with a totally different precipitation pattern (substantial summer rain) and
295 higher humidity. As a result, the cedar would be in competition with species that are in their optimal
296 zone (*Fagus orientalis* Lipsky, *Castanea sativa* Mill., *Carpinus* spp., *Quercus* spp., *Abies nordmanniana*
297 (Steven) Spach, *Pinus nigra* J.F. Arnold, etc.) and in suitable conditions for fungus outbreaks. It is
298 important to note that *C. libani* maps here shown correspond with suitability according to the
299 explanatory variables, where biotic factors were not considered by lack of them. The suitability of
300 the Black Sea Region and the Central Anatolia regions for the species indicated in the results of the
301 study is confirmed by the performances of the afforestation in the last 30 years in Turkey (Figure 1a).
302 Whereas, on the southern part of its area of distribution, pest outbreak (i.e. *Cephalcia tannourinensis*)
303 would be more recurrent and damaging since the insect proliferates under reduced soil moisture
304 and increased soil temperature (Nemer et al. 2014).

305 Study results indicate that annual rainfall is the best predictor of establishing successful
306 plantations. This is in concordance with those of Nemer et al. (2008) who stress the importance of
307 spring precipitations and winter snow melt for the growth of trees. Where the average annual
308 rainfall falls below 400-500 mm, even if the soil conditions are very favorable, the growth of the
309 cedar plantation is adversely affected (Ürgenç 1986; Karataş and Özkan 2017). This emphasizes that
310 climate characteristics are more effective than the other site characteristics for the height growth of
311 *C. libani*. In addition, it was determined that there is a positive relationship between height growth
312 and average high temperature, potential evapotranspiration, water excess, average temperature of
313 coldest month, average temperature of warmest month and average temperature of three summer
314 months.

315 316 5. Conclusions

317 The use of 13 GCMs and 6 algorithms makes our study robust and accurate. Migration might be
318 necessary for *C. libani* to cope with projected change. A similar trend has been detected in *Cedrus*
319 *atlantica* populations in Algeria where its southern distribution limit shows a high level of tree
320 mortality during recent decades (Slimani et al. 2014). Factors that are correlated with altitude seem
321 to be the most significant (Körner 2007). This is consistent with other tree species studied in the
322 Mediterranean basin (López-Tirado et al. 2018). Habitat suitability area results wider in the
323 forecasted scenarios than in the present period. These results can be useful to manage *C. libani*
324 natural and non-natural stands. Afforestation programs can be already carried out, aiming to face
325 the expected climate change.

326 **Supplementary Materials:** Figure S1: Suitability variation among the 6 algorithms in the present.

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Table 1. Variables used for Ecological Niche Modeling of *C. libani* distribution.

Variables	Label	Source
Topographic		
Aspect (degrees)	Asp	DEM
Slope (%)	Slo	DEM
Elevation (m)	Ele	DEM
Climatic		
Annual Mean Temperature (°C)	Bio1	WorldClim
Mean Diurnal Range (°C)	Bio2	WorldClim
Isothermality (Bio2/Bio7) × 100	Bio3	WorldClim
Temperature Seasonality (SD×100) (°C)	Bio4	WorldClim
Max Temperature of Warmest Month (°C)	Bio5	WorldClim
Min Temperature of Coldest Month (°C)	Bio6	WorldClim
Temperature Annual Range (°C)	Bio7	WorldClim
Mean Temperature of Wettest Quarter (°C)	Bio8	WorldClim
Mean Temperature of Driest Quarter (°C)	Bio9	WorldClim
Mean Temperature of Warmest Quarter (°C)	Bio10	WorldClim
Mean Temperature of Coldest Quarter (°C)	Bio11	WorldClim
Annual Precipitation (mm)	Bio12	WorldClim
Precipitation of Wettest Month (mm)	Bio13	WorldClim
Precipitation of Driest Month (mm)	Bio14	WorldClim
Precipitation Seasonality (Coeff. of variation)	Bio15	WorldClim
Precipitation of Wettest Quarter (mm)	Bio16	WorldClim
Precipitation of Driest Quarter (mm)	Bio17	WorldClim
Precipitation of Warmest Quarter (mm)	Bio18	WorldClim
Precipitation of Coldest Quarter (mm)	Bio19	WorldClim
Emberger index	Q	WorldClim
Continental index	Ci	WorldClim

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Table 2. Elevation, latitude and habitat suitability area for the current distribution and models in the present and forecasted scenarios. Values for the potential distribution in the present and forecasted scenarios were computed with cells whose suitability is either equal or over 50%.

		Current distr.	Pot. distr. present	RCP 4.5 2050	RCP 4.5 2070	RCP 8.5 2050	RCP 8.5 2070
Elevation (m)	Min.	16	194	0	0	0	12
	Max.	2819	3330	3889	3889	3889	4192
	Mean	1485	1376	1310	1419	1374	1481
Latitude (degree)	Min.	33° 40' 54"	33° 38' 54"	33° 18' 54"	33° 18' 54"	33° 19' 54"	33° 19' 53"
	Max.	41° 59' 54"	40° 26' 54"	42° 3' 54"	41° 58' 54"	41° 59' 24"	42° 5' 53"
	Mean	37° 17' 25"	37° 46' 22"	39° 10' 3"	39° 7' 56"	39° 8' 4"	39° 18' 5"
Habitat suitability area (km ²)		3,829	92,583	407,516	342,112	329,799	205,779

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Table 3. AUC values for each algorithm.

CSM	EnvScore	EnvDis	GARP	MaxEnt	SVM
0.88	0.68	0.99	0.88	0.64	0.91

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FIGURE CAPTIONS

Figure 1. a) Location of the study and area of occupancy of *C. libani* natural and planted stands (in green); b) *Cedrus libani* potential distribution in the present. Consensus map from the 6 algorithms used.

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Figure 2. *Cedrus libani* potential distribution in the forecasted scenarios: a) RCP 4.5 (2050), b) RCP 4.5 (2070), c) RCP 8.5 (2050) y d) RCP 8.5 (2070). Yellow colour shows not any potential distribution, whereas dark brown colour displays high potential distribution.

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Figure 3. Surface occupancy in the intermediate (RCP 4.5) and high emission scenario (RCP 8.5) for both periods (2050 and 2070); present is also shown.

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